

16th AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024):

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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PREFACE

Dear Colleagues,

The AgroStat biannual series of conference are driven by the Agro-Industry Group of the French Statistical Society (SFdS), which is a non-profit organisation bringing together researchers, engineers, teachers and statistics users (<https://www.sfds.asso.fr>). The 16th Edition of the AgroStat Conference (AgroStat 2024) will take place from the 3th to 6th September 2024 in the city of Bragança, Portugal, hosted and organised by the Polytechnic Institute of Bragança (IPB).

Bragança is a typically-Portuguese old town (Romanic origin dates back to the 10th century), located by the Natural Park of Montesinho – one of the wildest forest zones of Europe – and the Douro Valley – the third oldest protected wine region in the world; and surrounded by traditional villages of a distinctive rustic beauty. Bragança houses several traditional industries producing a myriad of local foods, such as cheese, fermented meats, wine, chestnuts and honey, which provide substantial economic sustainability to the region.

The AgroStat 2024 conference will reunite internationally recognised researchers and industrial organisations representatives, to take stock of advances in statistics, express their needs and to anticipate future challenges. The AgroStat 2024 conference will provide engineers, modellers, statisticians, developers and end-users, a unique opportunity to exchange knowledge and prospects around novel statistical methods applied to agri-food and sensory sciences. We expect to gather a significant number of delegates to participate in a comprehensive scientific programme that includes 5 keynote lectures, and oral communications, allocated in sessions focusing on the following themes: Sensometrics, Chemometrics, Experimental designs, Process control, Risk analysis, Big Data and Software tools.

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process, capabilities and maintenance of processing tools, etc. Altogether, they affect the reproducibility of final product characteristics representing deviations to standard, the production yield impacting the economic performance of the food manufacturing process, etc. In other words, the overall performance of a manufacturing process can be defined by considering several types of indicators such as economic, quality and environmental indicators. In order to improve the overall performance of a food manufacturing process, it is necessary to identify all sources of variability: in this view, having a global vision of all the measurements collected throughout the process could constitute a powerful lever for optimising production.

In this work, a multi-objective and data-driven approach is used to optimise the overall performance of the cheese manufacturing plant. In the industry, performance objectives are often conflicting, and need to be taken into account simultaneously, as proposed by this method. Machine learning method is implemented to model and explain the variability of each indicator defining the overall performance by using all the parameters collected over the course of one year. Several optimisations were implemented by changing the input parameters (composition of the raw milk) in order to understand how to adapt the process to several given situations.

Comparison of the optimisation scenarios reveals a need to adapt the manufacturing process to different conditions. Implementing a multi-objective approach to optimise overall performance provide industries a powerful decision support tool for controlling their process. To sum up, the development of a multi-objective method for maximizing the overall performance of complex processes through machine learning represents a major breakthrough for the food industry

Keywords: Multiobjective optimisation; Dairy industry; Global performance; Machine Learning

MODELING THE GROWTH DYNAMICS OF *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS* IN MOROCCAN JBEN SOFT CHEESE UNDER DIFFERENT STORAGE TEMPERATURES

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Understanding the growth behavior of pathogens in food products is critical for food safety. This study investigated the growth dynamics of *Staphylococcus aureus* CECT 976 in Jben goat's milk soft cheese made without starter culture, and stored at 8°C, 20°C and 37°C.

Lab-scale goat's Jben soft cheese samples were prepared following traditional methods and inoculated with *S. aureus* strain. Kinetic parameters such as initial and maximum microbial concentrations (SA₀, SA_{max}) and maximum growth rate (μ_{max} SA) were

estimated using Lotka-Volterra and Jameson-effect models considering the inhibitory effect (a_{21}) of indigenous lactic acid bacteria (LAB) on *S. aureus*.

The results showed significant temperature-dependent differences in *S. aureus* and LAB growth rates and maximum concentrations. At 8°C, *S. aureus* had a lower SA_0 and SA_{max} concentration, and a slower μ_{max} SA (1.054 days⁻¹, 1.089 days⁻¹ for Lotka-Volterra and Jameson-effect models). At 37°C, *S. aureus* showed a significant increase in μ_{max} SA (14.97 days⁻¹, 22.24 days⁻¹) and an increase in SA_{max} . Although the root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) values were lower for the Lotka-Volterra model, the fact that a_{21} was not found significant at any temperature suggested that the Jameson-effect model was a more parsimonious model. Thus, square-root secondary models for the maximum growth rate of *S. aureus* and LAB were developed from the Jameson-effect fitted values; and subsequently these two relationships were validated against growth data obtained at 30 °C.

These results provide insights into the temperature-dependent growth kinetics of *S. aureus* in goat's Jben cheese, which is a first step for ensuring the safety of these regional dairy products.

Keywords: Jben cheese; Microbial modeling; Predictive microbiology; Jameson effect; Lotka-Volterra; Lactic acid bacteria

BIOPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA AGAINST LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES IN HEAT-TREATED RECONSTITUTED MILK

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Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) play an important role in fermented products, by promoting desirable organoleptic properties, and by their antimicrobial properties limiting the growth of pathogenic bacteria. The objective of this study was to determine the growth kinetics of *Listeria monocytogenes* (LM) in heat-treated reconstituted milk, as affected by selected LAB strains *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*, *Lacticaseibacillus paracasei* and *Loigolactobacillus coryniformis* isolated from goats' milk cheeses.

Challenge tests of each LAB strain in monoculture and in coculture with LM in milk adjusted to three initial pH levels (5.5, 6.0 and 6.5) were performed. Inoculated milk samples were left to ferment at 12°C for 8 days. A pH-driven dynamic growth model was fitted in separate to the LM and LAB experimental curves from both monoculture and coculture experiments; and a Jameson-effect growth model was fitted only to the coculture growth curves. In monoculture, *L. mesenteroides*, when compared to the other LAB strains, showed the highest growth rates at the three initial pH levels; whereas in coculture,